

An Image Mosaicing Based Method for Bird Recognition on Edge Computing Devices

Dmitrij Teterja,¹ Jose Garcia-Rodriguez¹, Jorge Azorin-Lopez¹, Esther Sebastian-Gonzalez², Rita Elise van der Walt³, and MJ Booysen⁴

¹ Department of Computer Science and Technology, University of Alicante, Spain

² Department of Ecology, University of Alicante, Spain

³ Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering/ MIH Media Lab, Stellenbosch University, Stellenbosch, South Africa

⁴ Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Stellenbosch University, Stellenbosch, South Africa

dteterja@dtic.ua.es¹ jgarcia@dtic.ua.es¹ jazorin@ua.es¹
esther.sebastian@ua.es² 21574081@sun.ac.za³ mjbooyesen@sun.ac.za⁴

Abstract. Bird recognition is an important task in wildlife monitoring and conservation. However, traditional methods for bird recognition often require significant computational resources, making them impractical for use on edge computing devices. In this paper, we propose an image mosaicing-based method for bird recognition on edge computing devices. Our method combines image mosaicing and deep learning techniques to accurately identify bird species from a series of individual images. It achieves excellent accuracy of 97.37% with quick reaction times using compact, lightweight networks such as MobileNetV2. These results demonstrate the effectiveness and potential of our approach for real-time bird recognition on edge computing devices, making it suitable for a wide range of applications including monitoring and conservation of bird populations.

Keywords: bird recognition, deep neural networks, mosaic images, mosaic method, edge computing, mobile computing.

1 Introduction

Birds are essential to sustaining our ecosystem, performing critical ecological tasks such as pollination, seed dispersal, and soil fertilization. Biodiversity, which refers to the variety of animal species in an ecosystem, is vital for supporting life, providing food, purifying water, regulating the climate, and more [1]. For these reasons, many nations prioritize promoting biodiversity conservation and sustainable use [2]. Accurate identification of bird species is essential for conservation biology, biodiversity assessments, and monitoring of bird populations. Climate change has impacted the ability of many native species to provide ecosystem services, making it important to explore the relationship between biodiversity, ecological integrity, and ecosystem services in the future [3]. While some

countries focus on promoting the conservation of biodiversity and its sustainable use [2], others study the effects of climate change on ecosystems, biodiversity, and ecosystem services, as well as the implications for managing natural resources [5]. Automated technologies offer ornithologists the opportunity to classify bird images with high accuracy and anticipate spotted species using sounds, images, videos, or a combination thereof [4]. Such technologies can thus support monitoring and preservation efforts. However, even for humans, bird identification is a challenging task due to similarities between various species, differences in their shapes in images and vocalizations in sounds, and a lack of expertise among bird observers [9], where visual identification of birds in the wild can be time-consuming and prone to errors.

To address this need for rapid and reliable bird species identification tools, we propose a precise and effective bird detection and recognition system that operates on edge computing devices. In recent years, there have been significant improvements in bird species recognition models by computer vision experts [15]. An effective model should require minimal training time, be efficient, and be compatible with other mobile or edge computing devices [6]. We design an image mosaicing approach and evaluate its performance using contemporary deep CNNs on a sizable dataset of birds. Our findings demonstrate that compact, lightweight networks, such as MobileNetV2 and ResNet50, achieve excellent accuracy with quick reaction times. Our approach has the potential to improve bird identification accuracy and efficiency of the state-of-the-art, which could have practical applications in conservation and ecological research. In this study, we contribute to the field of image representation by using Mosaic images, evaluating and comparing deep neural network techniques, and optimizing for bird recognition in photographs captured in natural environments [6]. We compare cutting-edge techniques using several metrics, applied transfer learning and classifiers, and achieved a 99.51% F1-score accuracy. Our focus is on creating an efficient bird recognition system that can operate on a small edge-computing device placed in a wild setting to recognize bird behavior.

The structure of the paper is as follows: Section 2, Image Mosaicing-Based Method, provides an explanation of the model structure used for testing with our Mosaic images. Section 3, Experiments and Results, presents the conducted experiments and the achieved results, with a focus on the target mobile and edge-computing systems to ensure the deployability of the Mosaic technique in real-world environments.

2 Image Mosaicing-Based Method

In this section, we present our model structure for testing with Mosaic images captured from the wild environment on mobile or edge-computing devices. We leverage CNN models by utilizing transfer learning and partial re-training on our newly created dataset, which is represented in a Mosaic image format. We constructed Mosaic images by aligning images into a matrix structure, providing more information about the species in the same Mosaic image. Our approach is

Fig. 1: Diagram of the Mosaic images method. Blue denotes the learning stage and green denotes the recognition and identification stage.

based on convolutions, the primary property of CNN architectures, and combines multiple images of the same species into one. We trained and tested various models on the Mosaic dataset images, aiming to find the most compact yet well-performing approach for our purposes.

Figure 1 illustrates the process of the learning, recognition, and identification stages. In the learning stage, regular bird images are transformed into Mosaic images using an image mosaicing algorithm and stored in a dataset. These images are then used to train the top layers of deep convolutional neural network models until they achieve satisfactory performance. The next stage is bird identification, in which mosaic images are retrieved from the dataset and used for classification. The system produces accuracy metrics and a classification for each bird. In the next step, a camera system is used to capture images from wild environments, recognize birds, and then employ a similar pipeline where images of birds are combined using the image mosaicing algorithm and directly used as input for bird identification. The system then outputs accuracy metrics and classification results.

Our mosaicing method differs from the Mosaic data augmentation approach used in YOLOv4 [16], which generates a new compound image by aligning individual, cropped, and non-cropped images into rectangular grid sections, sometimes with their ground truths, using Mixout, Cutout, and CutMix algorithms. Instead, our Mosaic method combines multiple images of the same species into one. We trained various models on the Mosaic dataset images, aiming to find the most compact yet well-performing approach for our purposes.

We constructed the dataset by aligning images of the same species vertically and horizontally into a matrix structure, providing more information about the species in the same Mosaic image. Our approach capitalizes on convolutions, the primary property of CNN network architectures, where applying the same filter

across a Mosaic image enables the detection of a specific type of feature across the entire input image. This capability, known as translation invariance, answers the question of whether a feature is present rather than where it is present.

3 Experiments and Results

In this section, we report on our experimental results and provide explanations for the outcomes of each method. We converted Birds 500 Species dataset [7] of 80,085 images to 8,898 Mosaic images. These images were split into training, testing, and validation sets at a ratio of 60/20/20. Then we trained the models using the mini-batch gradient descent algorithm with a batch size of 32 and a 0.0001 learning rate. To prevent overfitting, we used five-fold cross-validation and early stopping for efficient hyperparameter optimization. The early stopping condition was based on the performance of the model on the validation set, and training was halted if the validation loss function did not improve for five consecutive epochs. Our evaluations were conducted on a machine with a 12th Gen Intel Core i5 12400F @2.5 GHz, 32GB RAM, and an Nvidia GeForce RTX 3060 8GB graphics card running on Ubuntu Linux 22.04 LTS.

Figure 1 shows the Mosaic image recognition pipeline with learning and recognition stages and two types of recognition - one where images are acquired from the Mosaic dataset and another from a trap camera device. In the learning stage, we process regular bird images from the Birds 500 Species dataset to create a new database of Mosaic images in a matrix form. These images are used for training of the eight pre-trained CNN models using transfer learning. Once the bird recognition model is trained, it is ready for recognition, which occurs in the recognition stage. Images are taken from the Mosaic Birds 500 Species dataset and used as input for the models. The results are probabilities given to each of the bird species. We evaluated classification performance using the Mosaic dataset and plan to test classification of images received from a trap camera device in future research. Trap camera classification will involve capturing images of a bird at given time intervals and combining them using image mosaicing, followed by class estimation.

We tested various CNN models, including ResNet50 [11], VGG16 [13], MobileNetV2 [10], EfficientNetB0 [6], Xception [8], InceptionV3 [12], DenseNet121 [14], and NASNetMobile [6], through transfer learning using both the original Birds 500 Species public dataset and our newly created dataset of Mosaic images. To produce inputs for our models, we read a Mosaic image consisting of nine randomly selected images of the same species only once across all Mosaic images. We did this to test the effect of downsizing images on final results when original information is lost. Prior to converting into Mosaic images, we resized all images to their smaller representations, approximately 75×75 pixels, and then resized the final image again to match the desired dimensions.

3.1 Results

This section details our process of evaluating and selecting models suitable for deployment on mobile or edge-computing devices for bird species recognition. We reviewed various studies and analyzed eight models using specific performance metrics, producing four graphs that show accuracy with respect to model size, number of parameters, CPU and GPU times per inference step. To train these models, we used transfer learning and our new Mosaic images dataset. The accuracy F1-score was used as the performance metric, measured using a five-fold non-shuffled cross-validation method. Our program reads all dataset images from a local disk into a matrix structure at startup, and downloads pre-trained models from a remote repository to a local disk. We trained each model using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.0001 and a categorical cross entropy loss function, with a maximum of 100 epochs for all training methods. The performance of the models is presented in Table 1 and in Figures 2 to 5.

Table 1: Model size, CPU time, GPU time and F1-score accuracy comparison with accuracy after transfer learning.

Model	Size (MB)	Top-1 Acc (%)	Top-5 Acc (%)	Parameters (Mill)	Time (ms) per step CPU	Time (ms) per step GPU	Acc (F1-score)	Mosaic Acc (F1-score)	Epoch	Placement (size, param, CPU, GPU, acc)
MobileNetV2	14	71.3	90.1	3.5	25.9	3.8	94.49	97.37	52	1/1/1/1/5
NASNetMobile	23	74.4	91.9	5.3	27.0	6.7	92.58	96.23	64	2/2/2/6/6
InceptionV3	92	77.9	93.7	23.9	42.2	6.9	93.32	93.20	63	6/6/3/7/8
EfficientNetB0	29	77.1	93.3	5.3	46.0	4.9	97.63	99.16	75	3/3/4/4/3
ResNet50	98	74.9	92.1	25.6	58.2	4.6	96.52	99.51	37	7/7/5/3/1
DenseNet121	33	75.0	92.3	8.1	77.1	5.4	96.36	99.34	49	4/4/7/5/2
Xception	88	79.0	94.5	22.9	109.4	8.1	94.38	96.11	55	5/5/8/8/7
VGG16	528	71.3	90.1	138.4	69.5	4.2	94.97	98.82	32	8/8/6/2/4

Table 1 presents the results of our evaluation of eight deep learning models for bird recognition using image mosaicing. These models were selected based on their performance among the available types. The table provides information on the sizes of the models (in megabytes), their Top-1 and Top-5 accuracy rates (in percentages), the number of parameters (in millions), and the CPU and GPU times per inference step. Additionally, the table presents metrics related to the post-transfer learning phase, including the F1-score accuracy of non-Mosaic images, the F1-score of Mosaic images, the number of epochs when the methods finished their computation, and the ranking of each model. In this table, the F1-score accuracy of non-Mosaic images is the accuracy computed with the original Birds 500 Species dataset images we used as input, in the same pipeline as the Mosaic images.

The first model, MobileNetV2, achieved the smallest model size, the fewest number of parameters, and the most efficient CPU and GPU performance, all ranking 1st among the tested models. However, it ranked 5th in accuracy, with ResNet50 achieving the highest accuracy (ranked 1st) and DenseNet121 ranking 2nd.

3.2 Analysis of the results

We conducted a comprehensive analysis of the results by comparing different parameters. Specifically, we evaluated the relationship between model size and accuracy, as shown in Figure 2. We observed that ResNet50 achieved the highest accuracy of 99.51%, but it was not the smallest model. On the other hand, MobileNetV2 had the smallest size and was ranked as the most compact model. However, InceptionV3, despite being the smallest model, showed the worst performance in terms of accuracy. It is also noteworthy that VGG16, with a size of 528MB, was the largest among all the models studied. For a general-purpose bird recognition system, we found that VGG16 and InceptionV3 models showed the poorest performance.

Fig. 2: Model Size vs Accuracy.

Results of the comparison Parameters vs Accuracy. The second graph (Figure 3) displays the relationship between the number of parameters of the models and their accuracy. While ResNet50 achieves the highest accuracy of 99.51%, it comes with a drawback of requiring larger number of parameters, resulting in a less size-efficient model. Conversely, MobileNetV2 offers a smaller parameter count, making it more size-efficient, albeit with lower accuracy compared to ResNet50, DenseNet121, EfficientNetB0. These networks strike a balance between parameter count and accuracy, making them suitable for a bird recognition and identification system with versatile applications.

Fig. 3: Model Parameters number vs Accuracy.

Results of the comparison CPU time vs Accuracy. The third graph (Figure 4) compares CPU-only systems in terms of accuracy. ResNet50 achieves the highest accuracy but is not the fastest, while MobileNetV2 is the fastest but slightly less accurate than ResNet50, DenseNet121, EfficientNetB0, and VGG16. The choice of the most suitable model should consider a trade-off between accuracy and processing time, depending on available computing resources. For installations without a GPU, ResNet50, DenseNet121, EfficientNetB0, VGG16, and MobileNetV2 are recommended.

Fig. 4: Model CPU time vs Accuracy.

Results of the comparison GPU time vs Accuracy. The fourth graph (Figure 5) illustrates the comparison of neural network models with GPU-enabled hardware in terms of accuracy. We observed that the computational times are significantly smaller, ranging from approximately 4 ms for MobileNetV2 to over 8 ms for Xception. The performances of ResNet50, EfficientNetB0, DenseNet121, and VGG16 are relatively similar, offering higher accuracy, while MobileNetV2 and

VGG16 are the most suitable options for high-precision systems due to their speed and accuracy, outperforming other models.

Fig. 5: Model GPU time vs Accuracy.

Our analysis suggests that smaller models tend to have faster computational times on both CPU and GPU systems. To explore the relationship between model size and accuracy, we refer to columns 8, 9 and 10 in Table 1, which report the f-1 score accuracy of each model after transfer learning using the regular Birds 500 Species dataset ("Acc (F1-score)"), the Mosaic images converted from the same dataset ("Mosaic Acc (F1-score)"), and the number of epochs it took for the loss function to plateau in the last five iterations ("Epochs"). Additionally, the "Placement" column ranks the accuracy of each trained network after transfer learning. Overall, the data indicate that smaller models tend to outperform larger ones in terms of computational speed, while still achieving competitive accuracy on our task.

4 Conclusion

We conclude that Mosaic images are more effective than plain bird species images for training, with transfer learning applied to ResNet50, DenseNet121, EfficientNetB0, and MobileNetV2. Each model has its advantages and disadvantages. ResNet50 is the most accurate, while MobileNetV2 offers lower power consumption and is smaller in size, making it suitable for resource-constrained environments. The actual choice of the model will depend on factors such as memory, CPU, or GPU type of the system. Future work will involve testing and validating various split Mosaic images to achieve better results for real-world bird images, recognizing bird species and behaviors in the wild. We considered previous research that focused on human recognition methods utilizing neural networks and trajectory analysis [17]. We also examined studies that explored trajectory analysis for describing and recognizing group activities [18]. Additionally, we reviewed a predictive method for early detection of global human behavior [19],

where the method utilizes the activity description vector (ADV) as a behavior descriptor, representing trajectories and activities in different scene regions. Our research has important practical implications for developing efficient and accurate bird identification tools and plan to extend their work to other domains beyond bird recognition.

Acknowledgment

We express our gratitude to the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 for their support of this research under the "CHAN-TWIN" project (grant TED2021-130890B-C21) and the AICARE project (grant SPID202200X139779IV0), as well as the HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-0 action number: 101086387, REMARKABLE, Rural Environmental Monitoring via ultra wide-Area networkS And distriButed federated Learning. We also extend our appreciation to Nvidia for their generous hardware donations, which enabled us to conduct our experiments.

References

1. Simon Upton, "Biodiversity and ecosystems", 2014, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, <https://www.oecd.org/env/resources/OECD-work-on-biodiversity-and-ecosystems.pdf>.
2. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, "Results of the Survey on the Coefficients Applied to Rio Marker Data when Reporting to the UN Convention on Climate Change and Biodiversity", DCD/DAC/STAT(2020)41/REV2.
3. Takafumi Ohsawa, "Idea paper: How are ecosystem services related to biodiversity and ecological integrity in each site under climate change?", 2022, Vol.37, Is.4, doi: 10.1111/1440-1703.12302.
4. S. Nawaz, A. Calefati, M. Caraffini, N. Landro and I. Gallo, "Are These Birds Similar: Learning Branched Networks for Fine-grained Representations," 2019 International Conference on Image and Vision Computing New Zealand (IVCNZ), Dunedin, New Zealand, 2019, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/IVCNZ48456.2019.8960960.
5. Sarah R. Weiskopf et al, "Climate change effects on biodiversity, ecosystems, ecosystem services, and natural resource management in the United States, Science of The Total Environment, Vol.733, 2020, 137782, ISSN 0048-9697, doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.137782.
6. Aldi Jakariaa et al., "Comparison of Classification of Birds Using Lightweight Deep Convolutional Neural Networks," Jurnal Elektronika dan Telekomunikasi (JET), Vol.22, 2022, pp.87-94, doi: 10.55981/jet.503.
7. Gerry, "BIRDS 510 SPECIES- IMAGE CLASSIFICATION", <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/gpiosenka/100-bird-species>.
8. A. Sungsir et al., "The Classification of Edible-nest Swiftlets Using Deep Learning," 2022 6th International Conference on Information Technology (InCIT), Nonthaburi, Thailand, 2022, pp. 404-409, doi: 10.1109/InCIT56086.2022.10067665.
9. Al-Showarah et al., "Birds Identification System using Deep Learning.", (IJACSA), Vol.12, No.4, 2021.

- Y. P. Huang et al., "Bird Image Retrieval and Recognition Using a Deep Learning Platform," in *IEEE Access*, vol.7, pp. 66980-66989, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2918274.
10. Ting-Wu Chin et al., "Towards Efficient Model Compression via Learned Global Ranking", 2019, doi: 10.48550/arXiv.1904.12368.
 - Gao Huang et al., "Densely Connected Convolutional Networks," 2017, doi: 10.48550/arXiv.1608.06993
 11. Xiang, W.; Song, Z.; Zhang, G.; Wu, X. "Birds Detection in Natural Scenes Based on Improved Faster RCNN." *Appl. Sci.* 2022, 12, 6094. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12126094>.
 12. Rahman, Md. Mahbubur et al. "Recognition of Local Birds of Bangladesh using MobileNet and Inception-v3." *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications* 11 (2020), DOI:10.14569/ijacsa.2020.01110840.
 13. Wu, Peng et al. "Classification of Birds Based on Weighted Fusion Model." 2021 7th International Conference on Big Data Computing and Communications (BigCom) (2021): 90-97.
 14. Mohammed Alswaitti et al., "Effective classification of birds' species based on transfer learning", *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, Vol. 12, No. 4, August 2022, pp. 4172-4184, ISSN: 2088-8708, DOI: 10.11591/ijece.v12i4.pp4172-4184.
 15. Y. P. Huang and H. Basanta, "Recognition of Endemic Bird Species Using Deep Learning Models," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 102975-102984, 2021, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3098532.
 16. Golnaz Ghiasi et al., "Simple Copy-Paste is a Strong Data Augmentation Method for Instance Segmentation", Submitted on 13 Dec 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2012.07177>
 17. J. Azorín-López, M. Saval-Calvo, A. Fuster-Guilló and J. García-Rodríguez, "Human behaviour recognition based on trajectory analysis using neural networks," *The 2013 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*, Dallas, TX, USA, 2013, pp. 1-7, doi: 10.1109/IJCNN.2013.6706724.
 18. J. Azorin-Lopez, M. Saval-Calvo, A. Fuster-Guillo, J. Garcia-Rodriguez, M. Cazorla and M. T. Signes-Pont, "Group activity description and recognition based on trajectory analysis and neural networks," 2016 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN), Vancouver, BC, Canada, 2016, pp. 1585-1592, doi: 10.1109/IJCNN.2016.7727387.
 19. Azorin-Lopez, J., Saval-Calvo, M., Fuster-Guillo, A. et al. "A Novel Prediction Method for Early Recognition of Global Human Behaviour in Image Sequences." *Neural Processing Letters*, 43, 363-387 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11063-015-9412-y>.